

1 Tire wear compounds, phthalates, and trace metals in the Kiel Fjord 2 (Germany)

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15 Abstract

16 Concerns about pollutants in the environment are increasing, with substances such as plastic additives
17 drawing particular concern due to their potential harmful effects on organisms. This study investigates
18 current levels of several contaminants in the Kiel Fjord. Some pose serious health risks to aquatic life.
19 In September 2022, water and sediment samples were collected from fifteen stations across the inner
20 and outer Kiel Fjord. The concentrations of selected phthalates, tire wear compounds, and heavy
21 metals were measured. Results indicate that the outer fjord has minimal contamination, while the
22 inner fjord contains several hotspots with significant pollutant concentrations. For example, the
23 highest levels of heavy metals were detected near Laboe and in deeper sediment layers (>6 cm) at
24 Wik. The maximum concentrations of phthalates were observed near Laboe, with elevated levels also
25 found near the city of Kiel and the Nord-Ostsee-Kanal. This study highlights the substantial
26 anthropogenic impact on the region.
27

28 Keywords

29 plastic compounds, tire wear, phthalates, heavy metals, Kiel Fjord
30

31 1. Introduction

32 Kiel Fjord is located in the northern part of Germany (54°19'–54°30'N; 10°06'–10°22'E). It has a North-
33 South extension of around 9.5 km and is part of the southwestern Kiel Bight in the Baltic Sea. Studies
34 on the pollution in Kiel Fjord are rare. Several potential areas in the fjord could serve as a source of
35 anthropogenic pollution, including the shipping ports, the military port, high ship traffic through Kiel

36 canal, fish and mussel farms, and one river inlet. Aquaculture in net cages (mariculture) is a particular
37 problem because it leads to selective changes in the pelagic system. As a result, it causes problems in
38 the environment due to contamination with various organic pollutants like antibiotics or fertilizer (e.g.,
39 Gesamp 1991). Krost et al. (1994) investigated the impact of floating fish farms in Kiel Fjord and found
40 that there were significant changes in the geochemistry beneath the net cages. The sediment there
41 was anoxic (1.5-3.5-fold higher than in the surrounding area), overgrown with sulphur bacteria and
42 almost completely free of macrofauna. Contrary to this, it has been found that the mussel farm
43 (*Mytilus edulis*), which was established in 2010, has the potential to increase water quality by removing
44 excess nutrients and making the water more transparent (Schröder et al., 2014).

45 The influence of shipping and the military largely altered the metal content of the sediments.
46 Consequently, the organic matter on the seabed is highly enriched in heavy metals such as copper,
47 iron, tin or lead (Nikulina et al., 2008). Tin can be found in particularly high concentrations in the
48 harbours because it was used as an antifouling agent on ships (Nikulina et al., 2008). Since lead has
49 been banned as an additive in gasoline, its content in the sediments decreased over the last few
50 decades (Nikulina et al., 2008).

51 Organic pollutants, such as additives from plastics, are another novel entities for the environment
52 regarding organisms' health. Plastics are ubiquitous contaminants that enter the marine environment
53 through different pathways including improper waste management and littering (Hahladakis et al.,
54 2018). In the Baltic Sea, microplastics (size between 1 and 5000 μm ; Klein et al., 2018) mainly result
55 from the fragmentation of large plastic debris into smaller pieces. Three different beaches in Kiel Fjord
56 were examined and an average pollution of 1.8-4.5 microplastic particles (fibres plus fragments) per
57 kg of dry sediment was found (Schröder et al., 2021). Between March 2018 and March 2019, Ory et
58 al., (2020) monitored microplastics concentrations in eight different stations in Kiel Fjord. Using a 300
59 μm mesh size, they found a stable and low entry of microplastics around 0.04 particles/ m^3 water.
60 Highest concentrations of microplastics were observed after rainfall and or snow/ice melt. The lowest
61 levels of microplastics were found near the wastewater treatment plant outflow, which shows the high
62 efficiency of their filtering system (Ory et al., 2020).

63 All plastics contain additives, which are mixed to the polymer during manufacturing to provide the
64 desired physical and chemical properties. For example, phthalic acid esters (phthalates) are commonly
65 used plasticizers to increase the flexibility of polymeric materials (Hahladakis et al., 2018) such as
66 polyvinyl chloride (PVC). Since additives are not chemically bound to the polymer, they can be released
67 into the environment and lead to exposure to organisms (Wei et al., 2018). Among different polymers,
68 PVC contains high amounts of phthalates (up to 50 wt%; Rochman, 2015) which can be released into
69 the aquatic environment over years to decades (Henkel et al., 2022). It has been shown that many

70 phthalates have harmful effects on organisms and they are considered endocrine disruptors (Liu et al.,
71 2013). In the environment, the release of phthalates can be influenced by environmental factors, such
72 as pH, salt content, and flow conditions (turbulence). In addition, photoaging can lead to the formation
73 of transformation products (Henkel et al., 2023; 2024). Phthalates and their transformation products
74 are concerning pollutants in the environment (Ren et al., 2018) and have been detected in water, the
75 atmosphere, soil, and in living organisms. Zhu et al. (2022) or Bergé et al. (2013) reviewed studies
76 reporting the global concentrations of phthalates. In the northwestern Mediterranean, a phthalate
77 concentration of 1.2 µg/L was measured in surface water near Marseilles (Zhu et al., 2022).
78 Concentrations of plasticizers in the Baltic Sea (Curonian Lagoon) range from 0.01 to 6.17 µg L⁻¹ (Lorre
79 et al., 2023), however, they are not known in Kiel Fjord.

80 In the last decade tire wear particles emerged as a strong environmental concern due to the release
81 of toxic chemicals (Challis et al., 2021). Tire wear particles (TWPs) are introduced into aquatic
82 environments through wet and dry deposition during events like rain, wind, and storms. Exposure to
83 tire particles and their leachates has been associated with various adverse effects on organisms (Halle
84 et al. 2020). Annually 6.1 million tons of tire wear particles can reach the environment, which account
85 for up to 10 % of the global source of microplastics (Kole et al., 2017). Urban Stream Syndrome is a
86 term describing the surface water draining from urban landscapes which leads to symptoms of
87 ecological degradation (Meyer et al., 2005). For example, 6PPD-quinone, a transformation product of
88 the widely used chemical additive 6PPD showed high toxicity to coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*)
89 and is linked to mass die-off after road wash events in the Pacific Northwest (Tian et al., 2021). The
90 concentration of road tire wear particles in aquatic systems increases more than 40 times during storm
91 events, leading to a tire wear particle input of 252-730 kg per storm event (Rauert et al., 2022).

92 This study aims to determine the current level of selected tire wear compounds, phthalates, and heavy
93 metals in Kiel Fjord. In September 2022, water and sediment samples were collected from seventeen
94 stations across the inner and outer regions of the Kiel Fjord. These samples were analyzed for the
95 presence of six phthalates, listed as priority pollutants by the EPA, along with three common
96 transformation products. Additionally, eighteen tire-derived compounds and several heavy metals
97 were measured. The data obtained from these analyses were used to construct pollution profiles,
98 delineating the distribution of these pollutants in both North-South (from Kiel Deep to Kiel City) and
99 East-West (from the outer Kiel Fjord, Strander Bucht to Laboe) directions. This comprehensive study
100 enabled the identification of areas within the Kiel Fjord exhibiting high levels of pollution, referred to
101 as 'hot spots'. This is the first study that deals with the pollution of tire wear compounds in the Kiel
102 Fjord. It provides information about the distribution and source of pollutants and highlights areas of
103 concern where further efforts are needed to reduce pollutant concentrations.

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2. Material and Methods

2.1. Kiel Fjord – geographical setting and hydrology

The southern inner part of the Fjord has an average width of 250 m, whereas the outer Fjord can expand up to 7.5 km (Nikulina et al., 2008). The sedimentation is mainly influenced by erosion and redeposition of material from the sea bottom (Seibold et al., 1971). The sediment in the Kiel Fjord is dominated by sand and mud, whereas the content of organic-bound carbon (C_{org}), sulphur and iron are generally higher in basins with mud (1 – 3% C_{org}) in contrast to sandy areas (3 – 5% C_{org}) (Seibold et al., 1971). The near bottom water and the sediments in the Kiel Fjord are well known for oxygen deficiency, especially during summer periods (Gerlach, 1984).

Kiel Fjord can be divided into a shallow inner part (inner Kiel Fjord) with water depths of 10 to 12 meters and an outer Kiel Fjord with depths up to 20 m. The Schwentine River is the unique source of freshwater into the Kiel Fjord (ca. 3.5 m³/s freshwater (Ory et al., 2020). Water masses remain stagnant most of the year as there are no substantial currents or regular movements of the water body and are mainly mixed by strong wind events (Rumohr, 2013). The Nord-Ostsee-Kanal is an artificial connection between the Kiel Fjord and the North Sea and was opened 1895 (Sartori 1891).

2.2. Sediment and water sampling

Both, water, and sediment samples were taken during a cruise on the research vessel R.V. ALKOR in September 2022 (28-30th). Detailed information about the stations and the transects is given in **Figure 1** and **Table 1**. The first transect (west to east) represents the border between inner and outer fjord. The second transect (north to south) covers the stations between the deepest point in the North (Kiel Deep) and the city Kiel in the South. Additional samples were taken on selected locations like the entrance of the river Schwentine or the Nord-Ostsee Kanal. At a total of 15 stations, water samples were taken with the CTD-rosette in surface and bottom waters and 50 ml sediment was collected with a box corer to examine organic components. At three stations (Site 1, 4 and 9), sediment samples were taken using a Rumohrlot down to a maximum depth of 9 cm. Immediately after collection, the sediment core was cut into 1 cm thick slices, with the top layer (fluffy layer) being separately taken out with a syringe. The sediments were used to study heavy metal content on the seafloor with depth. The pH of the water samples and the concentration of dissolved organic carbon were determined upon return in the laboratory - The DOC concentration in the water samples was 2.46+-0.166 mg/L and the pH was 7.93 +- 0.217 (average of all stations).

139 **Table 1.** Description of sampling sites including station name, location (latitude and longitude) and
 140 depth of water sampling (SW = surface water; BW = bottom water). S depicts the total water depth at
 141 the station. At all stations water samples (CTD) and sediment samples (box corer) were taken. Rumohr-
 142 core samples for metal analysis were taken at Site 1 (Strande), 4 (Wik) and 9 (Laboe).

Station	Lat	Long	SW depth [m]	BW depth[m]	S depth [m]
Site 1 (Strande)	54.433300	10.1885083	2.0	14.7	16.7
Site 2	54.415575	10.216120	3.1	8.8	10.8
Site 3	54.385861	10.176669	2.3	9.0	11.0
Site 4 (Wik)	54.352650	10.150129	2.4	7.8	9.8
Site 5	54.330267	10.152567	2.9	12.3	14.3
Site 6	54.332773	10.164676	2.8	10.6	12.6
Site 7	54.367670	10.188864	2.8	7.6	9.6
Site 8	54.370350	10.158500	2.6	9.6	11.6
Site 9 (Laboe)	54.420583	10.206817	2.6	13.3	15.3
Site 10	54.428426	10.195144	2.5	12.9	14.9
Site 11	54.489467	10.348333	2.6	17.1	19.1
Site 12	54.443081	10.262159	2.6	8.6	10.6
Site 13	54.404855	10.205233	2.5	12.9	14.9
Site 14	54.377672	10.184709	2.5	13.0	15.0
Site 15	54.353272	10.167071	2.6	11.5	13.5

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145 **Figure 1.** Map including all sampling stations in Kiel Fjord, stations where a Rumohr-core was taken for
146 metal analysis are indicated in black. Furthermore, two transects (South-North and East-West) are
147 highlighted in red boxes. These are depicted in transect plots in **Figures 5 and 6.**

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149 2.3. Processing sediment for trace metal measurements

150 For the metal analyses, sediment samples were subjected to a multi-stage digestion process on a
151 hotplate. First, aqua regia (1.5 mL HCl (30%) and 0.5 mL HNO₃ (65%), both of analytical grade) was
152 added to the samples. This mixture was then evaporated at 140°C to dryness. The dried residue was
153 then treated with a further 0.5 mL of HCl (30%) and 1.5 mL of HNO₃ (65%) and the mixture was heated
154 at 120°C for 12 hours. The samples were then dried again at 120°C and dissolved in 2 mL HNO₃ (65%).
155 Insoluble components such as silicates were removed by filtration. Metal concentrations in the
156 processed samples were determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS;
157 Agilent 7900 Single Quad ICP-MS in helium mode).

158 For all measured elements a standard error index was calculated. This index is based on the % from
159 the standard error and the mean value from all measurements along a station depth profile. For the
160 calculation, the standard error and the mean value of every single element for all 9 cm was
161 determined. In the next step, the percentage of the standard deviation from the mean value was
162 calculated. The higher this index is, the more the connections vary with depth.

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164 2.4. Processing samples and analysis of plastic compounds

165 Water samples were taken at fifteen stations at the surface (~2.5 m) and near the sea floor using 1 L
166 brown glass bottles. Details on the sampling locations are given in **Table 1.** To avoid bacterial growth
167 50 mg L⁻¹ of sodium azide (99 %, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, U.S.) were added
168 to the water samples. Sediment samples were taken at all stations in 50 mL clear glass Schott bottles.
169 All samples were stored at 8 °C and in the dark until further analysis.

170 The concentration of six phthalates (dimethyl phthalate (DMP), diethyl phthalate (DEP), di-n-butyl
171 phthalate (DBP), butyl benzyl phthalate (BBP), bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) and di-n-octyl
172 phthalate (DNOP)), three transformation products (mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), phthalic
173 acid and phthalic anhydride), and of 18 most prominent tire derived compounds (TDC) compiled from
174 the literature (Benzothiazole (BTH), 2-aminobenzothiazole (2-amino BTH), 5-methyl-1h-benzotriazole
175 (5-Me BTH), 2-methylbenzothiazole (2-Me BTH), 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (2-S BTH), 2-
176 hydroxybenzothiazole (2-OH BTH), p- Phenylenediamine (PPD), N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-1,4-
177 phenylenediamine (6PPD), 2-anilino-5- [(4-methylpentan-2-yl)amino]-cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione
178 (6PPD-Q), Aniline, N-Cyclohexyl-2- benzothiazolesulfenamide (CBS), 1,3-Diphenylguanidine (DPG),

179 N,N'-Diphenylthiourea (DPTU), 1,3-Dio- tolylguanidine (DTG), Hexa(methoxymethyl)melamine
180 (HMMM), N-Phenyl-2-naphthylamine (Neozone), 2'-methylenebis[6-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methyl-
181 phenol (AO22462), Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA)) was determined
182 in the water and sediments samples. (Spies et al., 1978; Huang et al., 2021; Tian et al., 2021; Mueller
183 et al., 2022).) Selected properties and a grouping of the compounds are given in the supplementary
184 **Table S1**.

185 Water samples were extracted using solid phase extraction with a vacuum extraction system
186 (Extraction Manifold, Waters, Vienna, Austria) and eluted using methanol (LiChrosolv®, VWR
187 Chemicals, Vienna, Austria). Dried sediments were extraction using ultrasonication with methanol.
188 Details on the extraction and elution of the water and sediment samples are provided in Supporting
189 Information S2. For the quantification of phthalates, transformation products and TDC, deuterated
190 standards (DEHP-d4, DEP-d4, phthalic acid-d4 and benzothiazole-d4, and 6PPDquinone-d5) were
191 added to the samples. The concentrations of the phthalates, transformation products and TDC were
192 determined using liquid chromatography- triple quadrupole mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS,
193 Supplementary Information S3). A recovery test was conducted to evaluate the extraction and elution
194 efficiency of the SPE system (Supplementary Information S5 and Table S4). Detailed information about
195 the sample processing is provided in the supplement. The software Ocean Data View (v. 5.6.5,
196 <http://odv.awi.de>, Schlitzer, 2023) was used to generate the concentration maps (Figs. 4, 5 and 6). For
197 interpolation, the built in DIVA (data-Interpolating Variational Analysis)-gridding software was used.

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199 **3. Results**

200 3.1. Trace metals in sediment samples

201 Northern stations (Strander Bucht (Site 1) and Laboe (Site 9)), exhibit a relatively stable concentration
202 of all examined metals within the top 9 cm of sediment (**Figure 2, supplementary figure 1**). In contrast,
203 the station near the marine harbour Kiel Wik (Site 4), displays a significantly higher standard error
204 index, particularly for the elements Zn, Cd, Sn, Pb, and also for Cu and As. Generally, the initial 5 cm of
205 sediment are quite homogeneous and exhibit low levels of heavy metals. However, beyond a depth of
206 6 cm, the concentration of several metals such as Pb, Zn, Cd, Sn, and Cu increases. The most
207 pronounced increase was observed for Sn and Pb, followed by Cd, Zn, Cu, and As. Interestingly, the
208 sediments from Laboe (Site 9) demonstrate an inverse trend for a few metals (Cu, Zn, Pb, As, Sn), where
209 the concentration of heavy metals increases closer to the surface. Nevertheless, the standard error
210 index for these samples is considerably lower compared to those from Tirpitz Hafen.

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213 **Figure 2.** Depth profiles of heavy metal concentrations measured in Kiel Fjord sediments at stations
 214 Laboe (orange), Strande (grey) and Wik (blue) in mg kg⁻¹. Error bars indicate standard error.

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216 3.2. Phthalates and tire wear compounds in sediment samples.

217 The distribution of phthalate and tire derived compounds in the sediment samples is depicted in **Figure**
 218 **3** and **Table 2**. Details on the concentration of each compound at each station are given in
 219 **Supplementary table 2**. The outer region of the Kiel Fjord, adjacent to Laboe, exhibited the highest
 220 concentration of plastic compounds, predominantly benzothiazoles. After categorizing these plastic
 221 compounds into groups (**Supplementary table 1**), distinct pollution 'hot spots' were identified for each
 222 group (**Figure 3**). The region near Laboe was found to have the highest concentrations of the

223 benzothiazoles (199 ng/g sediment; primarily 2-mercaptobenzothiazole – 83%) and AO2246 (91 ng/g).
 224 In the Nord-Ostsee-Kanal, peak concentrations of HMMM (0.28 ng/g), DBP (24.79 ng/g), DMP (4.88
 225 ng/g), and phthalic anhydride (9.79 ng/g) were detected (see **Supplementary table 1** for IUPAC name
 226 of the compounds). Near Kiel City, the sediment samples showed the highest concentrations of
 227 phthalic acid (4.21 ng/g), Neozone (2.50 ng/g), 6PPD (10.28 ng/g), BBP (6.04 ng/g), and DEHP (70.70
 228 ng/g).

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 230 **Figure 3.** Detailed distribution maps of the organic pollutants in the sediment; all sampling stations
 231 are depicted as white dots. a) sum of all measured plastic additives, b) vulcanisation accelerators, c)
 232 phthalates + transformation products, d) benzothiazoles (units of colouring: ng g⁻¹).
 233

234 3.3. Phthalates and tire wear compounds in water samples.

235 The highest level of plastic and rubber compounds (200-300 ng/L) in the surface water was observed
 236 near Laboe (**Table 2**). A comprehensive list of all measured values is provided in **Supplementary table**
 237 **3**. The sediment surface water samples revealed the highest concentrations of plastic compounds near
 238 Laboe (278 ng/L), Kiel City (228 ng/L), and around the Nord-Ostsee Kanal (213 ng/L) (**Figure 4**). The
 239 pollutant distribution differs slightly from that in the sediments. For instance, the maximum
 240 concentration of the vulcanization accelerator is located near Laboe, not Kiel City. While

241 benzothiazoles are predominantly found in Laboe, a significantly higher quantity of anilines is detected
242 near the Kiel Canal compared to Kiel City. A detailed analysis is depicted in **Figure 4**. Generally, the
243 bottom water exhibits a higher level of pollution than the surface water. Near Kiel City, the
244 concentrations of Aniline, HMMM, DMP, DEP, and DEHP in the surface water are 5.48, 0.13, 0.56, 0.74,
245 and 40.70 ng/L, respectively. In contrast, the concentrations of the same substances in the bottom
246 water are 10.46, 2.84, 2.14, 8.12, and 127.97 ng/L, indicating an increase of 190 % for Anillin, 2184 %
247 for HMMM, 439 % for DMP, 1097 % for DEP, and 314 % for DEHP towards the sediment surface.

249 **Figure 4.** Detailed distribution maps of the organic pollutants in the water samples (surface and
250 bottom); all sampling stations are depicted as white dots (units of colouring: ng g⁻¹). a) sum of all
251 measured plastic compounds (surface), b) phthalates + transformation products (surface), c)
252 vulcanisation accelerators (surface), d) benzothiazoles (surface), e) sum of all measured plastic
253 compounds (bottom), f) phthalates + transformation products (bottom), g) vulcanisation accelerators
254 (bottom), h) benzothiazoles (bottom).

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256 For a more comprehensive understanding of the concentration of the three most prevalent pollutant
257 groups (phthalates including transformation products, vulcanization accelerators, and benzothiazoles)
258 within the water column, the data has been represented in two transects (**Figures 5 and 6**). These
259 transects include a North-South transect extending from Kieler Tiefe (north) to Kiel City (south), and
260 an East-West transect spanning from Laboe (east) to Strander Bucht (west). In the north-west transect,
261 phthalates were found in the surface water in the inner fjord as well as in the deeper water masses
262 near the city. The concentration of vulcanization accelerators was higher in the surface water around
263 Laboe and slightly higher concentrations near Kiel City. The same pattern was observed for
264 benzothiazoles. In the east-west transect, the main source of vulcanization accelerators was Laboe. For
265 phthalates and benzothiazoles, Laboe showed also highest concentrations. In Strander Bucht also a
266 higher concentration of these two plastic compounds can be observed.

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271 **Figure 5.** Distribution maps of the organic pollutants in the water column on a South to North transect
 272 through the fjord. Interpolation between individual samples (white dots) was performed in ODV using
 273 DIVA gridding (units of colouring: ng g^{-1}). a) phthalates + transformation products, b) vulcanisation
 274 accelerators, c) benzothiazoles.

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278 **Figure 6.** Distributions maps of the organic pollutants in the water column on an East-West transect
279 from Strande (West) to Laboe (East) through the fjord. Interpolation between individual samples
280 (white dots) was performed in ODV using DIVA gridding (units of colouring: ng g^{-1}). a) phthalates +
281 transformation products, b) vulcanisation accelerators, c) benzothiazoles.

282 Table 2: Overview of the measured compounds in the Kiel Fjord.

Compound group	Compound	Conc. range in water	Conc. range in sediment
		(ng L ⁻¹)	(ng g ⁻¹)
Phthalates and transformation products	DMP	0.00 - 4.27	1.03 - 4.88
	DEP	0.79 - 9.16	1.63 - 6.46
	DBP	0.00 - 119.32	11.27 - 24.79
	BBP	0.00 - 4.78	0.63 - 6.04
	DEHP	0.00 - 127.97	18.37 - 70.70
	DNOP	n.d.	0.08 - 1.12
	MEHP	n.d.	0.20 - 0.58
	Phthalic acid	n.d.	1.75 - 4.21
	Phthalic anhy.	n.d.	2.95 - 9.79
Benzothiazoles	BTH	n.d.	0.00 - 32.68
	2-amino BTH	0.07 - 1.85	n.d.
	5-Me BTH	n.d.	n.d.
	2-Me BTH	n.d.	0.00 - 164.70
	2-S BTH	n.d.	n.d.
	2-OH BTH	0.00 - 29.98	0.00 - 2.11
	PPD	n.d.	n.d.
6PPD+transformation product	6PPD	n.d.	0.00 - 10.28
	6PPD-Q	n.d.	0.05 - 0.88
	Aniline	0.35 - 15.97	0.00 - 1.27
Vulcanization accelerator	CBS	n.d.	n.d.
	DPG	1.33 - 96.59	0.00 - 2.33
	DPTU	n.d.	n.d.
	DTG	0.00 - 29.35	0.00 - 0.10
	HMMM	0.00 - 2.84	0.00 - 0.28
	Neozone	n.d.	0.08 - 2.50
	AO2246	0.00 - 20.51	0.00 - 90.94
	BHT	n.d.	n.d.
	BHA	n.d.	n.d.

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285 4. Discussion

286 4.1. Metal pollution and their potential sources

287 Our investigation revealed significant variations in the concentrations of Cu, Zn, Pb, Cd, and Sn with
 288 sediment depth in the Kiel Fjord (**Figure 2**). In contrast, the other elements studied (V, Cr, Co, Ni, As,
 289 Mo) exhibited a relatively uniform distribution across all stations (Wik, Strander Bucht, Laboe).
 290 Notably, at Strander Bucht, the sediment metal concentrations of heavy metals (Cu, Zn, Pb, Cd, Sn)
 291 remained consistent with depth, implying that the concentration of these metals has remained stable
 292 over the past few decades. At Wik, however, the concentrations of Cu, Zn, Pb, Cd and Sn increase at a
 293 sediment depth > 6 cm. According to Balzer et al., (1987), the sedimentation rate in Kiel Fjord is around
 294 1 mm per year. Based on these data, it can be assumed that there has been a decrease in heavy metal
 295 pollution in this region in the last few decades. The naval base in Kiel near Wik has been active since

296 1865. Shipbreaking, recycling, or dismantling can release considerable amounts of heavy metals in the
297 surroundings (Sharifuzzaman et al., 2016). This fact is probably one of the main reasons for the metal
298 pollution in the Kiel Fjord in recent decades. The ban on organotin heavy metals in anti-fouling paints
299 for ships will also have had a positive contribution to reducing metal concentrations in the sediment
300 near shipyards.

301 The sediment in the Kiel Fjord is rich in organic matter, and research has demonstrated that metals can
302 adsorb and/or precipitate onto organic particles, such as live or dead algae, and accumulate therein
303 (Chugh et al., 2022). Bioaccumulation serves a crucial role in the transportation of heavy metals to
304 higher trophic levels (Salama et al., 2019). An inverse trend was observed compared to Kiel Wik.
305 Specifically, in Laboe, the concentrations of heavy metals, e.g., Cu, Zn, and Pb, are increasing over the
306 past few decades, occasionally reaching levels that have been recorded at Kiel Wik.

307

308 4.2. Organic pollution in the Kiel Fjord

309 Highest concentrations of phthalates including transformation products were measured in the water
310 near the city of Kiel (200 ng/L) and in the central fjord at the mouth of the North Sea-Baltic Sea Canal
311 (150-175 ng/L). These concentrations were a factor of 1000 lower than those observed for example,
312 in India or Brazil (Zhu et al., 2022). The phthalates analyzed in our study have further been measured,
313 for example, in the seamount area of the Tropical Western Pacific and the northwestern
314 Mediterranean Sea (Marceille Bay) at concentrations up to 12.97 ng/L (Zhang et al., 2019), 924 ng/L
315 (Paluselli et al., 2018), respectively.

316 In the environment, phthalates are mainly transformed through biodegradation, as hydrolysis and
317 photolysis rates in water are low. However, biodegradation leads to the occurrence of transformation
318 products that are harmful to many organisms (Zhu et al., 2022). Concentrations of phthalates and their
319 transformation products in sediments were summarized by Bergé et al. (2013). The level of pollution
320 in Europe, North America and developing countries varies between 0.01 and 115 mg/kg dry weight
321 sediment. In Germany, 0.21-8.44 mg/kg phthalates were detected in rivers (Fromme et al., 2002). The
322 sediment samples from Kiel Fjord generally showed low concentrations of these pollutants.
323 Concentrations in the outer fjord were around 0.04 mg/kg and those in the inner fjord between 0.06-
324 0.1 mg/kg, with the highest concentrations being found near Kiel city and near the Nord-Ostsee-Kanal.
325 It is known that even very low concentrations of endocrine disrupting chemical in the mg/kg range for
326 example, of DEP, DEHP or DMP are harmful to organisms, especially microorganisms. In the water
327 samples in Kiel Fjord, DEP (36.35%) and DEHP (26.96%) accounted for most of the phthalate pollution,
328 followed by DBP (18.37%), DMP (17.87%) and BBP (0.45%). DEP is widely used in plastics products and
329 can cause irreversible damage to the reproductive system in animals and humans (Zhu et al., 2022).

330 DEHP can also have a toxic effect on organs of organisms. Due to its low water solubility and
331 biodegradability, DEHP can sorb and accumulate in the sediment. In the sediment in Kiel Fjord, DEHP
332 accounts for 58 % of the phthalate pollution, which shows that this pollutant has also accumulated
333 significantly in the area we examined. DBP and DMP have carcinogenic effects for humans and have a
334 high potential for accumulation, as the hydrolysis half-life of these substances is approximately 20
335 years (Zhu et al., 2022). In the Kiel Fjord sediment, DBP accounted for around 29 % of the phthalate
336 pollution, while DMP only accounted for 4 %.

337 Less is known about vulcanization accelerators as pollution in marine environments. DPG and DTG
338 were detected in highest concentrations in Kiel Fjord among the list of 18 TDC. Studies have suggested
339 the endocrine-disrupting, neurotoxicity, and reproductive toxicity potential of DPG. (Shin et al., 2020;
340 Chibwe et al., 2021) There was only one location near Laboe in the water of Kiel Fjord where
341 particularly high concentrations of this additive were found. In contrast, significantly higher
342 concentrations were found in the sediment near Kiel city. In 2022, concentrations of DPG and another
343 tire derived compound 6PPD-quinone were measured in a river (Don River) in Canada (Johannessen
344 et al., 2022). A few hours after a rain event, 0.52 µg/L DPG and 2.85 µg/L 6PPD-quinone were
345 measured. The LC₅₀ for the *coho salmon* living there is 0.8 µg/L 6PPD and was therefore exceeded
346 many times (Johannessen et al., 2022). Concentrations of the 6PPD and 6PPD-quinone were reported
347 in the range of 1.0-11 and 0.43-3.0 ng/g in sediment samples collected at the coasts of South China
348 Sea (Zeng et al., 2023).. However, this both 6PPD and 6PPD-quinone were detected in water and
349 sediment samples in Kiel Fjord.

350 The last measured group of chemicals are benzothiazoles. Benzothiazoles like BTH are frequently used
351 as biocides and corrosion inhibitors. In indoor air samples from cars an elevated concentration of 148
352 ng/m³ BTH was observed which led to an inhalation intake of around 18 ng/kg body weight/day for an
353 adult human (Jeonghoon et al., 2024). The medial lethal dose LD₅₀ for rats was reported between 380-
354 900 mg/kg and varies between animals (Alderton et al., 2021). The high concentrations of
355 benzothiazoles in the Kiel Fjord were found next to Laboe and Strander Bucht. Few studies have
356 examined the toxic effect of BTH on aquatic organisms and found a sorption and bioaccumulation
357 potential of this pollutant (Liao et al., 2018). This could lead to further human exposure of BTHs
358 through consumption of seafood. Based on the BTHs concentrations measured, the estimated daily
359 dietary intakes of BTHs through the consumption of mollusks were higher in children and teenagers
360 compared to those in adults (Jia et al., 2019). The benzothiazoles concentration in the contaminated
361 part of the Kiel Fjord was between 25-30 ng/L. Peng et al., (2020) reported sub-lethal concentration
362 for *Bradysia odoriphaga* of 0.473 µg/L which is about the factor 10 higher than measured in the Kiel
363 Fjord. A reduced algae growth of *Selenastrum capricornutum* was observed at concentrations of 0.68

364 mg/L which is similar to the LD₅₀ for the common water indicator water flea *Daphnia magna* (Jia et
365 al., 2019).

366 Apart from this, other pollutants such as microplastics, pharmaceuticals, or nutrients like nitrogen and
367 phosphorus are also of concern in human affected areas. In further studies it is desirable to examine
368 such substances or nutrients in the Kiel Fjord in order to get a complete picture of the current state of
369 pollutants in this region. For tire-derived compounds studies on their concentrations in marine
370 environments remain limited, despite their detection frequency, bioaccumulation potential in various
371 aquatic ecosystems and human exposure potential. Future research should prioritize understanding
372 the distribution, fate, and ecological risks of TDCs, with particular attention to their persistence and
373 accumulation in marine organisms.

374

375 **5. Conclusions**

376 This study conducted a comprehensive examination of trace metals, tire wear compounds, and
377 phthalate plasticizers in the Kiel Fjord. In the outer fjord extending to the Kieler Tiefe, the
378 concentrations of all measured compounds were low, often below the detection limit. However, in the
379 inner fjord, certain hot spots were identified. Locations close to Kiel City exhibited increased
380 concentrations of plastic compounds in both water and sediment. A decline in metal pollution over
381 the past decades was observed for the nearby military port, Wik. Conversely, the Laboe region showed
382 increasing trace metal concentrations and elevated levels of the assessed organic pollutants. While the
383 exact sources of these pollutants could not be determined in this study, the exposure of the Kiel Fjord
384 to human activity was illustrated using both traditional (trace metals) and modern (plastic compounds)
385 compounds. Further studies are necessary to clarify the impact of the enriched pollutants on
386 organisms. It is important to investigate the interaction of pollutants on higher organisms as well as on
387 microorganisms to figure out how the food web will be affected by them.

388

389

390 **Data statement**

391 All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article.

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393

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406 **6. References:**

407 Alderton, I., Palmer, B. R., Heinemann, J. A., Pattis, I., Weaver, L., Gutiérrez-Ginés, M. J., ... &
408 Tremblay, L. A. (2021). The role of emerging organic contaminants in the development of
409 antimicrobial resistance. *Emerging Contaminants*, 7, 160-171.

410 Asimakopoulos, A. G., Wang, L., Thomaidis, N. S., & Kannan, K. (2013). Benzotriazoles and
411 benzothiazoles in human urine from several countries: a perspective on occurrence,
412 biotransformation, and human exposure. *Environment international*, 59, 274-281.

413 Babenerd, B., & Gerlach, S. A. (1987). Bathymetry and sediments of Kieler Bucht. In *Seawater-
414 Sediment Interactions in Coastal Waters: An Interdisciplinary Approach* (pp. 15-31). Berlin,
415 Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

416 Balzer, W., Erlenkeuser, H., Hartmann, M., Müller, P. J., & Pollehne, F. (1987). Diagenesis and exchange
417 processes at the benthic boundary. In *Seawater-Sediment Interactions in Coastal Waters: An
418 Interdisciplinary Approach* (pp. 111-161). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

419 Bergé, A., Cladière, M., Gasperi, J., Coursimault, A., Tassin, B., & Moilleron, R. (2013). Meta-analysis
420 of environmental contamination by phthalates. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 20,
421 8057-8076.

422 Challis, J. K., Popick, H., Prajapati, S., Harder, P., Giesy, J. P., McPhedran, K., & Brinkmann, M. (2021).
423 Occurrences of tire rubber-derived contaminants in cold-climate urban runoff. *Environmental Science
424 & Technology Letters*, 8(11), 961-967.

425 Chibwe, L., Parrott, J. L., Shires, K., Khan, H., Clarence, S., Lavalle, C., ... & Rochman, C. M. (2022). A
426 deep dive into the complex chemical mixture and toxicity of tire wear particle leachate in fathead
427 minnow. *Environmental toxicology and chemistry*, 41(5), 1144-1153.

428 Chugh, M., Kumar, L., Shah, M. P., & Bharadvaja, N. (2022). Algal Bioremediation of heavy metals: An
429 insight into removal mechanisms, recovery of by-products, challenges, and future opportunities.
430 *Energy Nexus*, 100129.

431 Dietrich, G. (1950). Die natürlichen Regionen von Nord-und Ostsee auf hydrographischer Grundlage.
432 *Kieler Meeresforschungen*, 7(2), 35-69.

433 Fromme, H., Kuchler, T., Otto, T., Pilz, K., Müller, J., & Wenzel, A. (2002). Occurrence of phthalates and
434 bisphenol A and F in the environment. *Water research*, 36(6), 1429-1438.

435 Gerlach, S. A. (1984). Oxygen depletion 1980-1983 in coastal waters of the Federal Republic of
436 Germany.

437 Gesamp, IIMO/FAOAJnescorJ(IHO/IAEAAJNAJNEP) 1991: Reducine. environmental impacts of coastal
438 aquaculture. RepStud. 47:35 pp.

439 Ghosh, S., & Sahu, M. (2022). Phthalate pollution and remediation strategies: a review. Journal of
440 Hazardous Materials Advances, 6, 100065.

441 Hahladakis, J. N., Velis, C. A., Weber, R., Iacovidou, E., & Purnell, P. (2018). An overview of chemical
442 additives present in plastics: Migration, release, fate and environmental impact during their use,
443 disposal and recycling. Journal of hazardous materials, 344, 179-199.

444 Halle, L. L., Palmqvist, A., Kampmann, K., & Khan, F. R. (2020). Ecotoxicology of micronized tire
445 rubber: Past, present and future considerations. Science of the Total Environment, 706, 135694.

446 Henkel, C., Hüffer, T., & Hofmann, T. (2022). Polyvinyl chloride microplastics leach phthalates into the
447 aquatic environment over decades. Environmental Science & Technology, 56(20), 14507-14516.

448 Henkel, C., Lamprecht, J., Hüffer, T., & Hofmann, T. (2023). Environmental factors strongly influence
449 the leaching of di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate from polyvinyl chloride microplastics. Water Research,
450 242, 120235.

451 Henkel, C., Hüffer, T., Peng, R., Gao, X., Ghoshal, S., & Hofmann, T. (2024). Photoaging enhances the
452 leaching of di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate and transformation products from polyvinyl chloride
453 microplastics into aquatic environments. Communications Chemistry, 7(1), 218.

454 Huang, W., Shi, Y., Huang, J., Deng, C., Tang, S., Liu, X., & Chen, D. (2021). Occurrence of substituted
455 p-phenylenediamine antioxidants in dusts. Environmental Science & Technology Letters, 8(5), 381-
456 385.

457 Johannessen, C., Helm, P., Lashuk, B., Yargeau, V., & Metcalfe, C. D. (2022). The tire wear compounds
458 6PPD-quinone and 1, 3-diphenylguanidine in an urban watershed. Archives of environmental
459 contamination and toxicology, 1-9.

460 Jia, J., Zhu, Q., Liu, N., Liao, C., & Jiang, G. (2019). Occurrence of and human exposure to
461 benzothiazoles and benzotriazoles in mollusks in the Bohai Sea, China. Environment international,
462 130, 104925.

463 Jeonghoon Park, Hyejin Yun, Chungsik Yoon, Kiyoung Lee, Kyung-Duk Zoh. Suspect and non-target
464 screening of chemicals in household cleaning products, and their toxicity assessment. Environmental
465 Engineering Research 2024, 29 (1) , 230123-0. <https://doi.org/10.4491/eer.2023.123>

466 Krost, P., Chrzan, T., Schomann, H., & Rosenthal, H. (1994). Effects of a floating fish farm in Kiel Fjord
467 on the sediment. Journal of Applied Ichthyology, 10(4), 353-361.

468 Klein, S., Dimzon, I. K., Eubeler, J., & Knepper, T. P. (2018). Analysis, occurrence, and degradation of
469 microplastics in the aqueous environment. Freshwater microplastics: emerging environmental
470 contaminants?, 51-67.

471 Kole, P. J., Löhr, A. J., Van Belleghem, F. G., & Ragas, A. M. (2017). Wear and tear of tyres: a stealthy
472 source of microplastics in the environment. International journal of environmental research and
473 public health, 14(10), 1265.

474 Li, Z. M., & Kannan, K. (2023). Determination of 1, 3-Diphenylguanidine, 1, 3-Di-o-tolylguanidine, and
475 1, 2, 3-Triphenylguanidine in Human Urine Using Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass
476 Spectrometry. *Environmental Science & Technology*.

477 Liao, C., Kim, U. J., & Kannan, K. (2018). A review of environmental occurrence, fate, exposure, and
478 toxicity of benzothiazoles. *Environmental science & technology*, 52(9), 5007-5026.

479 Liu, Z., Ye, W., & Little, J. C. (2013). Predicting emissions of volatile and semivolatile organic
480 compounds from building materials: a review. *Building and Environment*, 64, 7-25.

481 Lorre, E., Bianchi, F., Vybernaite-Lubiene, I., Měžíně, J., & Zilius, M. (2023). Phthalate esters delivery
482 to the largest European lagoon: Sources, partitioning and seasonal variations. *Environmental
483 Research*, 235, 116667.

484 Meyer, J. L., Paul, M. J., & Taulbee, W. K. (2005). Stream ecosystem function in urbanizing landscapes.
485 *Journal of the North American Benthological Society*, 24(3), 602-612.

486 Müller, K., Hübner, D., Huppertsberg, S., Knepper, T. P., & Zahn, D. (2022). Probing the chemical
487 complexity of tires: Identification of potential tire-borne water contaminants with high-resolution
488 mass spectrometry. *Science of The Total Environment*, 802, 149799.

489 Nikulina, A., Polovodova, I., & Schönfeld, J. (2008). Environmental response of living benthic
490 foraminifera in Kiel Fjord, SW Baltic Sea. *eEarth*, 3, 37-49.

491 Paluselli, A., Fauvelle, V., Schmidt, N., Galgani, F., Net, S., & Sempere, R. (2018). Distribution of
492 phthalates in marseille bay (NW Mediterranean Sea). *Science of the total environment*, 621, 578-587.

493 Rauert, C., Charlton, N., Okoffo, E. D., Stanton, R. S., Agua, A. R., Pirrung, M. C., & Thomas, K. V.
494 (2022). Concentrations of tire additive chemicals and tire road wear particles in an Australian urban
495 tributary. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 56(4), 2421-2431.

496 Ren, L., Lin, Z., Liu, H., & Hu, H. (2018). Bacteria-mediated phthalic acid esters degradation and
497 related molecular mechanisms. *Applied microbiology and biotechnology*, 102, 1085-1096.

498 Rochman, C. M. (2015). The complex mixture, fate and toxicity of chemicals associated with plastic
499 debris in the marine environment. *Marine anthropogenic litter*, 117-140.

500 Rumohr, J., Walger, E., & Zeitzschel, B. (Eds.). (2013). *Seawater-sediment interactions in coastal
501 waters: an interdisciplinary approach (Vol. 13)*. Springer Science & Business Media.

502 Sartori, A. (1891). *Kiel und der Nord-Ostsee-Kanal*. ES Mittler und Sohn.

503 Salama, E. S., Roh, H. S., Dev, S., Khan, M. A., Abou-Shanab, R. A., Chang, S. W., & Jeon, B. H. (2019).
504 Algae as a green technology for heavy metals removal from various wastewater. *World Journal of
505 Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 35, 1-19.

506 Sharifuzzaman, S. M., Rahman, H., Ashekuzzaman, S. M., Islam, M. M., Chowdhury, S. R., & Hossain,
507 M. S. (2016). Heavy metals accumulation in coastal sediments. *Environmental remediation
508 technologies for metal-contaminated soils*, 21-42.

509 Schröder, T., Stank, J., Schernewski, G., & Krost, P. (2014). The impact of a mussel farm on water
510 transparency in the Kiel Fjord. *Ocean & coastal management*, 101, 42-52.

511 Schröder, K., Kossel, E., & Lenz, M. (2021). Microplastic abundance in beach sediments of the Kiel
512 Fjord, Western Baltic Sea. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28, 26515-26528.

- 513 Seibold, E., Exon, N., Hartmann, M., Kögler, F. C., Krumm, H., Lutze, G. F., ... & Werner, F. (1971).
514 Marine geology of Kiel bay. Kramer.
- 515 Spies, R. B., Andresen, B. D., & Rice Jr, D. W. (1987). Benzthiazoles in estuarine sediments as
516 indicators of street runoff. *Nature*, 327(6124), 697-699.
- 517 Tian, Z.; Zhao, H.; Peter, K. T.; Gonzalez, M.; Wetzel, J.; Wu, C.; Hu, X.; Prat, J.; Mudrock, E.; Hettlinger,
518 R.; Cortina, A. E.; Biswas, R. G.; Kock, F. V. C.; Soong, R.; Jenne, A.; Du, B.; Hou, F.; He, H.; Lundeen, R.;
519 Gilbreath, A.; Sutton, R.; Scholz, N. L.; Davis, J. W.; Dodd, M. C.; Simpson, A.; McIntire, J. K.; Kolodziej,
520 E. P. A Ubiquitous Tire Rubber–Derived Chemical Induces Acute Mortality in Coho Salmon. *Science*
521 (80-.). 2021, 371 (6525), 185–189. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abd6951>
- 522 Nájera-Martínez, M., Pérez-Cruz, A., Dzul-Caamal, R., & Vega-López, A. (2021). Are the Endogenous
523 Levels of Divalent Heavy Metals Responsible for the Oxidative Stress Response on Freshwater
524 Phytoplankton Communities?. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*, 232, 1-12.
- 525 Ory, N. C., Lehmann, A., Javidpour, J., Stöhr, R., Walls, G. L., & Clemmesen, C. (2020). Factors
526 influencing the spatial and temporal distribution of microplastics at the sea surface—a year-long
527 monitoring case study from the urban Kiel Fjord, southwest Baltic Sea. *Science of the Total*
528 *Environment*, 736, 139493.
- 529 Peng, X., Zhu, Z., Xiong, S., Fan, Y., Chen, G., & Tang, C. (2020). Tissue distribution, growth dilution,
530 and species-specific bioaccumulation of organic ultraviolet absorbers in wildlife freshwater fish in
531 the Pearl River catchment, China. *Environmental toxicology and chemistry*, 39(2), 343-351.
- 532 U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. Priority Pollutant List. 2014, 1–2
- 533 Wang, Y., Li, X., Yang, H., Wu, Y., Pu, Q., He, W., & Li, X. (2024). A review of tire wear particles:
534 Occurrence, adverse effects, and control strategies. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 283,
535 116782.
- 536 Wei, W., Bonvallot, N., Gustafsson, Å., Raffy, G., Glorennec, P., Kraus, A., ... & Mandin, C. (2018).
537 Bioaccessibility and bioavailability of environmental semi-volatile organic compounds via inhalation:
538 A review of methods and models. *Environment international*, 113, 202-213.
- 539 Zeng, L., Li, Y., Sun, Y., Liu, L. Y., Shen, M., & Du, B. (2023). Widespread occurrence and transport of p-
540 phenylenediamines and their quinones in sediments across urban rivers, estuaries, coasts, and deep-
541 sea regions. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 57(6), 2393-2403.
- 542 Zhang, J.; Zhang, X.; Wu, L.; Wang, T.; Zhao, J.; Zhang, Y.; Men, Z.; Mao, H. Occurrence of
543 Benzothiazole and Its Derivates in Tire Wear, Road Dust, and Roadside Soil. *Chemosphere* 2018, 201,
544 310–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.03.007>
- 545 Zhang, Q., Song, J., Li, X., Peng, Q., Yuan, H., Li, N., ... & Ma, J. (2019). Concentrations and distribution
546 of phthalate esters in the seamount area of the Tropical Western Pacific Ocean. *Marine pollution*
547 *bulletin*, 140, 107-115.
- 548 Zhu, Z., Rao, R., Zhao, Z., Chen, J., Jiang, W., Bi, F., ... & Zhang, X. (2022). Research progress on
549 removal of phthalates pollutants from environment. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 355, 118930.